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THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICE IN MEDIATING THE SKILLS AND POTENTIALITIES OF STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Special Education has changed over the years. There was a belief that a person with a disability should not be included in the social environment because they are incapable. Today, it is understood the need for inclusion to facilitate the development of that person, as well as provide means of greater interaction between people. but the teacher is not always ready to deal with this student with a disability. When we talk about teacher training, we must take into account factors such as availability of time, area of expertise, and professional development, among others. For better professional training it is necessary to develop work in consonance with cognitive and socio-emotional skills, aiming at a better performance with the student and consequently better teaching and learning. The activities should be concentrated on the higher forms of cognitive work: creating, applying, analyzing, and evaluating, with the support of their peers and teachers. In summary, means moving events that were traditionally done in class out of the room classroom, according to Lage Platt and Treglia (2000). Technologies have certainly helped education professionals to provide resources that help the process of learning and it is up to the educator to apply these resources in the best way, to promote the learning and intellectual evolution of these students.

KEYWORDS: Specialized Educational Service. Inclusion. Teaching. Teaching Practice

INTRODUCTION

This article demonstrates how working with Inclusion is not an easy task, it takes a lot of dedication. The Professor of Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE) performs meticulous work that is completely individualized, from plans, interviews, reports, case studies, evaluation, and adaptation of activities.

The AEE teacher must develop a work that encompasses all instances of the school, the management and pedagogical team, the teachers in the common room, the family, and especially the students in the regular room with the students served in the School Units. If there weren't so many existing difficulties with Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE), we are currently facing a health crisis. And now how to get the job done? Will we be able to have a positive result?

In this sense, the SEA teacher's main objective is to develop stimuli in students that are indispensable for full development, through pedagogical, technological, and educational resources, contributing significantly to independence and autonomy. To do so, it is necessary to have qualifications in Pedagogy or a degree in non-critical areas in the municipality; the priority is to be an effective servant of SEDUC, who has completed a postgraduate course in the field of Special Education. Know the national guidelines of the Special Education Policy and the guidelines issued by the Superintendence of Modalities and Themes; special needs/Special Education Management; • act in line with the other Programs of the Regional Coordination of Education, under the coordination of the Pedagogical Advisory of the Regional Coordination, via Inclusion Mediator; work in the Multifunctional Resource Rooms - and in the Specialized Educational Service Rooms - AEE, complementing and supplementing the pedagogical action carried out in the common classroom, with students with disabilities, autism spectrum disorders/ASD and high abilities/giftedness; subsidize the pedagogical activities of the educational units based on continuing education activities, guiding the Regent Teachers with regard to the teaching-learning process of students with disabilities, global developmental disorders, high abilities/giftedness; articulate actions with the pedagogical coordination,

involving the Regent Teacher and the Pedagogical Support Professional, for the implementation of an inclusive formal educational practice, making the curriculum more flexible and developing evaluation processes that consider the levels of development and the cognitive and socio-affective areas of the development; guide, support and collaborate with the preparation of the Student Learning/Development Report, bimonthly and annually, for students with Intellectual Disability and/or TGD/ASD to participate in meetings, meetings, seminars, courses and other actions promoted by SEDUC / SMTE/GEE/CRE; participate in the elaboration of the educational unit's internal regulations, as well as the Pedagogical Political Project, providing guidance on the institutionalization of the AEE offer and on the pedagogical action of inclusive education; subsidize and guide Regent Teachers, Pedagogical Support Professionals, Libras Interpreters, with regard to the specificities of students with disabilities, global developmental disorders/autistic spectrum disorder, high skills/giftedness .

Education is the way of building knowledge and necessary actions to integrate human beings into society. This concept is divided into two moments: informal education, received in the family core, and erudite, or formal, education received through academies. Throughout history, we realize that the educational process has been a need sought by man. In rock art, there were already indications of attempts at education in a more formal sense, even with the objective of survival.

In the West, Greek antiquity allowed its citizens to deepen their knowledge through academies. Plato had his school, although in a different way than what we understand today as an academic school environment. However, it was in Greece the beginning of studies and the creation of sciences through philosophy.

However, inclusive education is something new in the history of Brazil. It is known that the first special school was created at the time of D. Pedro II – the emperor who was a great lover of knowledge – in the 50s of the 19th century. The school served deaf-mute and visually impaired students. However, at that time there was great prejudice against people who had disabilities, leaving them on the margins of society and denying them contact with people

considered “normal”.

In the 1920s and 1930s, with the Escola Nova, people with disabilities were understood as cases of medical pathology. New School teachers, however, introduced education-oriented psychology studies and education-oriented intelligence tests, which classified or excluded students who were considered intellectually retarded.

Subsequently, the Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB nº 4024/61) provided for the integration of special students, at that time called exceptional, in the general education system and financial support from the government to the private sector that was willing to offer education for the specials. Around 1969, 80% of special education institutions were private, thus excluding low-income people, in addition to the separation between the “exceptional” and the “normal”.

Only with the CF of 1988 and the new LDB of 1996 did the school reach the milestone of inclusive education. In item III of article 208 of the CF, it establishes that the State must guarantee specialized assistance to people with disabilities, preferably in the regular education network. The Law of Guidelines and Bases of Education of 1996, in item III of article 4, establishes free specialized assistance to students with special needs, preferably in the regular education network.

With the Salamanca Declaration of 1994, it is established that those with special educational needs must have access to regular schools, which must accommodate them within a child-centered pedagogy.

Despite so many advances in the legal field, guaranteeing rights to people with disabilities, the school and teacher training courses still have certain deficiencies. The school environment has been changing and, little by little is becoming more inclusive. As for teacher training courses, there is still only general information about special education, and special education teachers need to seek additional training to better serve their students.

Assistive Technology is still a new term, used to identify the entire arsenal of Resources and Services that contribute to providing or expanding

the functional abilities of people with disabilities and consequently promoting independent living and inclusion. It is also defined as “a wide range of equipment, services, strategies and practices designed and applied to alleviate problems encountered by individuals with disabilities” (Cook and Hussey • Assistive Technologies: Principles and Practices • Mosby – Year Book, Inc., 1995). The concept in Brazil, by the Technical Assistance Committee - CAT, instituted by ORDINANCE No. 142, OF NOVEMBER 16, 2006 proposes.

Assistive Technology is an area of knowledge, with an interdisciplinary characteristic, which encompasses products, resources, methodologies, strategies, practices, and services that aim to promote functionality, related to the activity and participation of people with disabilities, disabilities or reduced mobility, aiming at their autonomy, independence, quality of life and social inclusion.

JUSTIFICATION

As neither all you students have accessed The computers It is cell phones, it was necessary to resort to the relatives creating one group with your students It is to work with the per video calls It is Shipping activities ‘via WhatsApp of parents and O teacher himself made an appointment individual for to help O student to answer online.

It is important to insert the context in which I, the researcher, am being inserted. I started working in education in 1994, when I passed a public in the city of Morrinhos, State of Goiás. I worked at State School Alfredo Nasser, the first Reference School for Inclusion in Morrinhos to receive special students as a literacy teacher and also as a facilitator of the Laboratory in Computing Educational (LIE) It is a coordinator Pedagogical.

Inclusion, in fact, only happens when there are responses to differences. so the schools must adopt practices pedagogical that enable people with disabilities to meaningful learning, which recognizes and value the knowledge that they are capable in to produce, observing O your rhythm It is your possibilities. One aspect relevant is O’s knowledge of theoretical specificities surrounding autism disability.

According to the Law of Guidelines and Base of

National Education - LDBEN n.9.394/96, public students of special education are considered those with special needs resulting from innate or acquired factors, of a temporary or permanent nature, that is, those who present: Physical Disability, Hearing Impairment, Deafness, Visual Impairment, Disability Intellectual Disability, Multiple Disability, Deafblindness, Global Developmental Disorders – PDD, High abilities/giftedness.

Thus, to discuss the importance of service education effective I propose to discuss some aspects that we deem important for The effectiveness of the inclusion full of teaching with autism It is a deficiency of intellectual at Network Regular of Teaching. In agreement with good (1999):

“Within the current conditions of Brazilian education, there is no way to include children with needs educational special at the teaching regular without support skilled, what offer to the teachers of these classes, guidance It is assistance”.

Thus, inclusive education offers adequate teaching to differences to the needs of each student and should not be seen from the side or in isolation, but as part of the regular system. Therefore, the essential question for the effectiveness of this concept is whether The training proper is to be continued for teachers (SANT’ANA, 2005; GLAT & FERNANDES, 2005).

You challenges faced for the educator front The policy in education inclusive levels expressive when it treats the inclusion of students with pervasive expressive disorders in development. These challenges present themselves as a result of the reduced training professional referent The portion component of needs educational specials. Teacher training is an aspect that deserves emphasis when addressing inclusion. Many prospective teachers feel insecure and anxious before the possibility of receiving a child.

There is a general complaint from students of pedagogy, degree, and teachers: “No I went prepared to lead with children with deficiency” (LIME, 2002, p.40).

Teacher training is indeed a necessity, becoming essential, however, we have to take into account urgently that such professionals must have

conditions for what these qualifications be effected It is what not stay only in plans. Then The majority of our professionals from the areas of educational work in two The three shifts, that pilgrimage in between shifts It is until same schools, make it difficult It is become impracticable The your participation in the qualifications offered, whether online, in person or hybrid with special needs in the room of class.

Educating a person with Pervasive Developmental Disorder is an experience that leads educators to review and question their conceptions about development, education, normality, and professional competence. this relationship put proof of the skills of educators. As to help those students The approach whether in way of meanings and significant human relationships. what means we can employ to help them communicate, to attract your attention It is interesting in the world? No, we have answers ready, however, we intend to offer the opportunity to reflect together on that theme so we find possible ways.

Any approach about O topic he must reference your pioneer Leo Kanner It is Hans Asperger who, separately, published your first works about those disorders. Kanner, in 1943, described The condition of eleven children considered special, with characteristics different from a concept that was very much in vogue in the era, schizophrenia childish.

Per one far away time, to the researches It studies about of theme they were guided for the conception from the psychomotricity, this It is, you Disorders global they were Classified us groups of psychoses. These theories were overcome It is today it is described that autism is linked to genetic causes and associated with causes environmental. From the 1980s onwards, the conceptions that perceive the Disorders Global/Invasive as disobey behavioral. faction (2005, P. 19) define what:

People with Pervasive Developmental Disorders (PDD) have, and common severe and invasive damage in the various areas of development, (skills in intervention Social reciprocal, in communication or presence in behaviors and/or interests stereotyped – activities It is movements I repeated you) It is each one differs from other

through of some characteristics individualized. (...)

Still for this author, there are five subtypes of PDD: Autistic Disorder, Rett's, Asperger's, Childhood Disintegration (PDD), and Pervasive Disorder Development without other Specification (TID-SOE). Students with Disorders global of Development are those that present one frame in alteration at the development neuro psychomotor, commitment in the relations social, at communication or motor stereotypies.

In that specter, the MEC defines what O Service Educational Specialized - AEE, whose function is to identify, develop and organize pedagogical and educational resources accessible to eliminate the barriers to The full participation of the students, considering your specific needs. This service complements and/or supplements the training of the students with views The autonomy It is independence at school and out of it.

Special education services and resources are those who ensure conditions in access to the curriculum per quite from the promotion from the accessibility of teaching materials, spaces, and equipment, to communication systems It is information and to the set of activities in school.

We start from the premise that teachers, in their initial training, are not prepared to work in a classroom with students with special needs educational specials. Like this, our search to understand O paper of specialized educational service, after specific training to work in the rooms of support and the use of assistive technologies.

For so much O goal in our search It is to analyze The importance of specialized educational service, discussing the implications of techniques in the process of mediation of skills It is the potentialities of the students with deficiency.

The steps of this research were guided by the specific objectives: a) to list the several learning tools and their uses used in the community school; b) list arguments in favor of the use of assistive technologies in the process education of students with disabilities; c) identify the aspects that facilitate and/or hinder the learning process of special students. d) Identify the use of assistive technologies as a tool facilitator in teaching

learning to students with deficiencies. It is) Identity to the difficulties that you teachers face It is resisted to the use of technologies assistive.

Know The reality of research already developed about The theme allowed us to see with bigger clarity The reality about The which we were researching, we delimited our research strategy with the definition of the type of search It is we opted for per one search qualitative.

When we work with observation, and interacting with your subjects It is with The reality in search, that methodology Show yourself most suitable because it allows the researcher one bigger flexibility in data collection and analysis.

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH CONTEXT

In the research, an investigation was carried out at the CEPI Alfredo Nasser State School, located on Avenida Prefeito Manoel Lemos de Mendonça s/nº Setor Oeste, Morrinhos – GO.

The institution's management team, consisting of a director and a pedagogical coordinator, provided free access for all research to be carried out.

RESEACH FOCUS

We opted for the qualitative methodology in which we developed the search for data in the field research. Experiencing reality allowing to observe it closely allows the researcher to develop a critical sense based on the theoretical perspective that underlies the look of the research.

The research has an exploratory character and the researcher, according to Rodrigo (2008), has the power not only to describe the situation without intervention but is also capable of having a great analytical range and questioning and confronting different situations, as well as generating new ones. theories and questions for future investigations.

Such characteristics overlap with the general characteristics of qualitative research. It can therefore be said that the approach is qualitative. This investigation is understood as one in which:

[...] the scientist is at the same time the subject and

the object of his research. Research development is unpredictable. The researcher's knowledge is partial and limited. The purpose of the sample is to produce in-depth and illustrative information: whether it is small or large, what matters is that it is capable of producing new information. (DESLAURIERS, 1991, apud. SILVEIRA AND GERHARDT, 2009.P.32).

This is a useful method when the phenomenon to be studied is large and complex and cannot be considered outside the context in which it naturally occurs. It is an empirical study that seeks to determine or test a theory and has interviews as one of the most important sources of information. Through them, the interviewee expresses his opinion on a given subject, using his interpretations.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The survey covered the universe of twenty-one special education professionals, who were invited to respond to a questionnaire containing about twenty-two objective questions and one subjective, and their results were analyzed throughout the entire process. SEARCHED POPULATION Teachers who work in special education and at the CEPI Alfredo Nasser State School, located at Avenida Prefeito Manoel Lemos de Mendonça s/nº Setor Oeste, Morrinhos – GO.

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

Data collection was carried out by applying a questionnaire and analyzing the reports of professionals who worked in the area of inclusion and special education. The questionnaire was answered by teachers who work in the AEE at the school and sought, from this data collection, to cover as many considerations as possible so that no pertinent question was left unaddressed.

DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE

Data were analyzed using the Excel program. The tabulation of the data allows checking the trends shown when the data are gathered, bringing to light the reality of a given situation

CONCLUSION

Certain that it wouldn't be easy, the teachers from

Apoio and AEE began to fight for innovative and more attractive resources.

And even before this unique situation, we had students without an internet connection and unmotivated, which was aggravated by this pandemic situation because, in addition to teachers having difficulties in presenting online classes and dealing with technological tools, doubts arose about how to attract students. students and also about evaluating the class.

Logically, when working with classes that have students with disabilities, the challenges are even greater, and it is necessary to think of efficient ways to communicate with them at a distance and, above all, how to present accessible content, among other details.

As not all students have access to computers and cell phones, it was necessary to resort to family members, creating a group with students and working with them through video calls and sending activities via WhatsApp to parents and the teacher himself set up an individual time to help the student. to respond online.

It is important to include the context in which I, the researcher, am being inserted. I started working in education in 1994, when I passed a public contest in the city of Morrinhos, State of Goiás. I worked at the Alfredo Nasser State School, the first Reference School for Inclusion in Morrinhos to receive special students as a literacy teacher and also as a facilitator of the Educational Informatics Laboratory (LIE) and Pedagogical Coordinator.

I worked as a Special Education Coordinator at the Regional Undersecretary of Education, in 2018, I returned to my duties as a Special Education teacher at the Alfredo Nasser State School.

Every barrier that a student with a disability encounters in the classroom is also encountered in distance learning. And this difficulty is often aggravated by the lack of preparation of the families of these children and young people, who, in addition to having to teach the given subject, must deal with the specificity of each student. 88 Each child has its characteristics and differences. There is no standard to be used with all children. The cases must be observed with a singular look,

not as a whole. In addition to the help of mediators, many students undergo continuous treatment with therapists, psycho-pedagogues, and speech therapists, in parallel so that they can follow the teaching in classrooms. It is noticeable that the use of assistive technologies contributed to the development of remote classes in 2020 and has much more to contribute in the coming years.

However, for professionals to be more confident when teaching their classes and for their students to be able to better absorb what is given to them, greater initiatives are needed.

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